

White lupin breeding: integrating phenotypic selection under organic conditions with marker assisted selection

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White lupin (*Lupinus albus*, L.) is an underutilised legume with high agronomic value, particularly for increasing nitrogen through biological fixation in organic farming. It also has great potential as ingredient in plant-based protein foods.

FiBL is conducting a pre-breeding programme with the aim of developing breeding material with increased anthracnose resistance, low alkaloid content and adapted maturation time for Central Europe. FiBL collaborates with gzpk (non-profit breeding organization) to jointly develop varieties for market-release.

The pathogen *Colletotrichum lupini*, agent of the anthracnose disease, can cause severe to complete yield loss. In white lupin, anthracnose resistance is polygenically controlled, no complete resistance was observed and only few sources of resistance were identified.

Lupin grains contain toxic and bitter quinolizidine alkaloids (QAs). QAs are water-soluble and can be removed from the grain by water-based debittering. This is laborious, uses large quantities of water and reduces lupin use. Hence, low QA content is a highly important breeding target. Alkaloid accumulation in the seeds has been described to be controlled by multiple loci, one major locus, *pauper*, with known causal mutation, and several other loci reported, but not genetically mapped.

Since both anthracnose resistance and QA content are complex traits, a multi-method approach is envisaged to speed up variety development. The aim of our study is to define strategies for combining phenotypic selection under organic conditions with molecular marker-based approaches that are affordable in our small-scale organic breeding programme.

Marker-trait associations for anthracnose resistance and low-alkaloid content have been identified through GWAS, Genomic Prediction and Bulk Segregant Analysis. PCR-based markers have been developed based on the identified associations from own studies and literature in order to apply marker assisted selection (MAS).

We present (i) the results of field phenotypic selection vs MAS for anthracnose resistance, (ii) the mapping of a novel major QTL for alkaloid content (present in cv Dieta) and (iii) the application of MAS to alkaloid gene stacking in a population from a cross designed to segregate for two low-alkaloid genes (Dieta×Frieda).

Research co-funding: DIVINFOOD (EU ID:101000383), LiveSeeding, (EU ID:101059872, SERI and UKRI), LUPINNO SUISSE (FOAG ID:2020/51) and LupiSMART (BLE ID:2825EPS049).